

Agricultural Land-Use Effects on Soil Cation Exchange Capacity, Organic Carbon and Total Nitrogen in Soil Aggregate Sized Fractions in Ile-Ife, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study determined the distribution of organic carbon (OC), cation exchange capacity (CEC) and total nitrogen (TN) associated with soil aggregates across land use types in Ile-Ife, Nigeria. Six agricultural land-use types were considered which were undisturbed secondary forest, continuously cropped land, paddock, oil palm, cocoa and teak plantations at the Teaching and Research Farm, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. Soils samples were randomly collected from each land use at 0-15 and 15-30cm soil depths in three replicates. The samples were segregated into four aggregate classes, <math><250\mu\text{m}</math>, 63-250 $\mu\text{m}</math>, 250 $\mu\text{m}</math>-1mm and 1-2mm respectively. The following analyses were carried out on the whole soil: particle size distribution, soil pH, CEC, OC and TN while CEC, OC and TN were carried out on different soil aggregate fractions. Data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance using SAS software and means were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test at $p \leq 0.05$. Results showed that OC, TN and CEC were more associated with smaller sized soil aggregates (<math><250\mu\text{m}</math>) across all the land-use types, except under oil palm plantation, which had most of its SOC associated with 1-2mm sized soil aggregate. In the whole soil, continuously cultivated land had the least OC and TN while secondary forest surprisingly had the least CEC. The study revealed that aggregate size <math><250\mu\text{m}</math> contributes the most to soil nutrient available. Therefore, conservative land-use practices (such as conservative tillage, mulching, manuring etc.) that protect the loss of soil micro-aggregates (<math><250\mu\text{m}</math>) especially to erosion should be adopted for sustainable land-use.$$

Keywords: Organic carbon, Land-use, Soil aggregate and Soil nutrient.

Effets de l'utilisation des terres agricoles sur la capacité d'échange cationique du sol, le carbone biologique et l'azote total dans les fractions granulométriques du sol à Ile-Ife, Nigéria

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Résumé

L'avenir de l'agriculture biologique au Nigeria dépend dans une large mesure de la demande de produits biologiques par les consommateurs. Cependant, les consommateurs peuvent ne pas

exiger des produits dont ils ne sont pas au courant ou sur lesquels ils disposent d'informations limitées. Dans cette étude, l'évaluation de la notoriété des produits alimentaires biologiques a été réalisée. La procédure d'échantillonnage à plusieurs degrés a été utilisée pour sélectionner 120 répondants utilisés dans l'étude. Des données primaires ont été collectées sur la connaissance par les répondants des aliments biologiques et des caractéristiques socio-économiques qui ont été analysées à l'aide de statistiques descriptives (fréquence, pourcentage, moyenne et type d'écart) et d'une analyse de score composite. Les résultats ont montré que 55% des répondants étaient des femmes avec un âge moyen et une taille de ménage de 49 ± 12 ans et 4 ± 1 personne, respectivement. Moins de 50% des répondants savaient que les aliments biologiques sont plus naturels avec un goût de qualité (43,3%) et sans conservateurs (49,2%), leur production est respectueuse de l'environnement (43,3%) et leur consommation favorise une vie saine (35,8%). Le niveau de sensibilisation des répondants était élevé avec environ 39,2% et 50% des répondants ayant des niveaux de sensibilisation élevés et modérés, respectivement. Les résultats de la désagrégation du niveau de connaissance selon certaines caractéristiques ont révélé que le niveau de sensibilisation était plus élevé chez les femmes (40,9%), les jeunes (50,0%), ayant fait des études secondaires (46,9%) et à revenu élevé (48,6%). L'étude a donc recommandé que plus d'éclaircissements et d'éducation sur les attributs et l'importance des produits alimentaires biologiques, en particulier parmi les hommes sans instruction, à faible revenu et les membres plus âgés de notre société.

Mots clés: produits chimiques synthétiques, aliments biologiques, consommateurs, organisme génétiquement modifié.

Introduction

Profitable agriculture needs proper management of land and soil resources on a sustainable basis. Soil physical and chemical properties often decline with conversion of forest to arable farm. Mostly, frequent cropping reduces soil aggregate stability, causes loss of soil organic carbon and total nitrogen, increased compaction and bulk density (Chisci and Zanchi, 1981; Paul *et al.*, 2017; Akinde *et al.*, 2020). Hence, soil management practices should be geared towards understanding how soil quality can be maintained and enhanced (Weil and Islam, 2000). Soil management practice is an essential factor in sustaining soil quality which depends on the knowledge of soil response to land-use practices over time (Gelaw *et al.*, 2013). Agricultural land-use is when a typical land is devoted to crop production, rearing of livestock and fish farming to produce food for human. For the land to bring out its best produce, soil structure, its aggregate, water movement and nutrient availability within the soil are essential within the soil.

Soil structure refers to the arrangement of soil particles and voids spaces in them. It influences

retention and transmission of fluids in the soil including aeration and infiltration. It can also be termed as shape and size arrangement as well as packing of particles into identifiable units called aggregates or peds. Soil aggregate is a discrete unit of soil particles bound to one another as separate from adjacent particles. The space between the aggregates provides pore spaces for exchange of air and water retention. Good soil aggregation is usually most desirable for plant growth especially in the critical stage of germination and seedling establishment. Oades and Water (1991) and Schmidt *et al.*, (2011) proposed that micro aggregates are within the size range of less than (<) 20-250 μ m. Snyder and Vazquez (2005) also reported that in micro-aggregate of 63-250 μ m in diameter, bonding is generally strong enough that the aggregates are stable to slaking upon direct immersion of air-dry soil into water. Differentiation of soils by aggregate size distribution have been used to evaluate impacts of land-use (Jastrow, 1996). Land-use and management affect soil aggregation and aggregate stability (Cerdeira, 2000). At the microscopic level, clay and organic matter act as bridges between the sand and silt particles, producing micro-aggregates in the soil

(Mclaren and Cameron, 1996). Aggregate size distribution is another major physical characteristic of the soil that strongly affects soil and its resistance to erosion and degradation. It is also considered to be an indicator of soil structure (Pachepsky and Rawls, 2003). It is therefore important to maintain soil aggregate so as to prevent soil loss; and protect soil efficiency and productivity.

Soil organic carbon (SOC), cation exchange capacity and total nitrogen contents play a crucial role in sustaining soil quality, crop production and environmental quality (Bauer and Black 1994; Robinson *et al.*, 1994) due to their effects on soil physical, chemical, and biological properties (Sainju and Kalisz, 1990). Organic carbon (OC) content of soil aggregates influence aeration and water movement while the SOC content of bulk soil affects water-holding capacity (Symeonakis *et al.*, 2007). The presence of SOC in different aggregate sizes is imperative for soil quality assessments (Curtin and Mullen, 2010; Li *et al.*, 2016).

The lower the aggregate size of the soil, the higher the CEC because the smaller sized particles, clay, contributes most to the exchange site (Arnaud *et al.*, 2018). Soil exhibits CEC mainly because clay particles and soil organic carbon in the soil tends to be negatively charged. The major source of CEC in the mineral fractions comes from clay. Improper land-use system has adverse effects on the soils. Severe soil deterioration reduces organic matter and clay contents in soil which often leads to loss of soil capacity to hold and release nutrients (Arnaud *et al.*, 2018). It may also cause important changes in soil physical and chemical characteristics which can affect soil quality. As far as we know, information on how soil aggregate and associated CEC, SOC and TN changes with changes in agricultural land-use in humid tropical area of Sub-Saharan Africa is rare. Hence, our quest for sustainable soil use for smart food production towards food sufficiency for our ever increasing global human population in areas with similar climate and land-use worldwide.

Therefore, there is the need to assess how land-use affects soil aggregate size distribution, soil CEC, SOC and TN within soil aggregate size

fractions. The main objectives of this study was to determine the effect of agricultural land-use on CEC, SOC and TN within soil aggregate size fractions.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out at the Teaching and Research Farm of the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. It is a region within the humid zone of Southwestern part of Nigeria. Ile-Ife lies between Latitudes 7° 32' N and 7° 33' N and Longitudes 4° 33' E and 4° 35' E and has different types of land-use. The area is about 200 metres above mean sea level. The climate is hot with distinct dry and rainy seasons. The area experiences approximately eight months (March-October) of annual rainfall that is bi-modal in distribution pattern with peaks in July and September. It has about four months (November-February) of dry season each year, though irregularity may occur in the rainfall distribution pattern over the years. The mean annual rainfall is about 1526.8mm (Akintola, 1986). Soil orders associated with this land-use types are Ultisol. Ultisols are strongly leached, acid forest soils with relatively low native fertility. They have a sub-surface horizon in which clays have accumulated, often with strong yellowish or reddish colours resulting from the presence of Fe oxides (USDA, 2014). They are derived from coarse-grained granite, gneisses and pegmatites which were identified as the bedrock of the soils of Iwo Association (Smyth and Montgomery, 1962). The six different land-use types considered in this study are: undisturbed secondary forest, continuously cropped land, paddock, oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*), cocoa (*Theobroma cacao*), and teak (*Tectona grandis*) plantations. These land-use were established about 35 years before this study except paddock and continuous cropped land-use which was established 20 years ago. Akinde *et al.*, (2020) gave detailed description of the land-use types including vegetal cover and management practices in each land-use.

Soil samples were randomly collected from different land-use types at two depths (0-15cm and 15-30cm) using sampling tube. Each land-use was divided into three replicates based on their

physiography (upper, middle, and lower slope). Collected soil samples were air dried, gently crushed and sieved through a 2mm mesh sieve. Exactly 2400g of soil was then placed on Endecott test sieve shaker (SER No: 6437) containing four sets of sieves to separate the soil into four different aggregate classes (<63 μ m, 63-250 μ m, 250 μ m - 1mm and 1-2mm).

On each aggregate class, particle size distribution was determined by the hydrometer method (Gee and Or, 2002). Soil pH in 0.01 M CaCl₂ was measured by WalkLAB electrode pH meter (Peech *et al.*, 1953). Cation exchange capacity (CEC) of the aggregate size classes under each land-use and the whole soil were determined using 1N ammonium acetate at pH 7 (Ross and Ketterings, 2011), Soil organic carbon (SOC) was determined colorimetrically following dichromate digestion method (Nelson and Sommers, 1996). Total nitrogen (TN) was determined by digestion procedure described (Bremner, 1996). Due to inadequacy in the quantity of <63 μ m sized soil aggregate fraction, only CEC was determined on <63 μ m sized soil aggregate fraction. While all parameters (CEC inclusive) were determined on all other soil aggregate fractions and whole soil. All data were analysed using SAS software (9.2 version).

Analysis of variance was carried out and significant means were separated using Duncan's new multiple range test at 0.05 levels of probability.

Results and Discussion

The soil textural class of the different land-use types were found to be sandy loam except for that of paddock plantation at the 0-15cm soil depth, teak plantation at the 15-30cm soil depth soil and cocoa plantation soil at both 0-15 and 15-30 cm soil depths, which were sandy clay loam (Table 1).

This is an indication that paddock, teak and cocoa plantation contain an appreciable amount of clay.

The pH of the whole soil was not significantly different across the land-use types and highest values were observed under cocoa (6.0) and forest (5.9) at both 0-15cm and 15-30cm soil depths. Thus, the soil reaction range classified as slightly acidic under cocoa land-use whereas that of forest was moderately acidic (Brady and Weil, 2002; Adepetu, 1994). The higher values of pH under cocoa land-use could be resulting from higher organic matter content due to higher amounts of plant residues at the soil surface (Wang *et al.*, 2013). Rainfall leaches basic cations away from soil exchange sites and their position are taken over by Al³⁺ and H⁺ which are acid forming and soil acidification is likely as a result of leaching.

Table 1: Texture and soil pH under different agricultural land-use

Land-use	← 0-15cm depth →				← 15-30cm depth →					
	Particle size			Texture class	Soil pH (cacl ₂)	Particle size			Texture class	Soil pH (cacl ₂)
	Sand	Silt	Clay			Sand	Silt	Clay		
← (gkg ⁻¹) →			← (gkg ⁻¹) →							
Paddock	680	60	260	Scl	5.3ab	720	80	200	Sl	5.1b
Oil palm	730	90	180	Sl	4.7b	770	70	160	Sl	4.6b
Teak	700	110	190	Sl	5.5ab	720	70	210	Scl	5.2ab
Forest	740	100	160	Sl	5.9a	780	90	150	Sl	5.8a
Cocoa	660	100	240	Scl	6.0a	560	100	340	Scl	5.3a
Cont. crop	720	100	180	Sl	4.7b	740	60	200	Sl	4.9b

Means with the same letter on a column are not significantly different (P<0.05) according to Duncan's New Multiple Range Test.

Scl – Sandy, clay loam, Sl – Sandy loam

Distribution of cation exchange capacity, soil organic carbon and total nitrogen in the soil aggregate class fractions at 0-15 and 15-30cm soil depths

Soil organic carbon associated with 63µm-250µm sized soil aggregate fraction was significantly the greatest going by the Duncan New Multiple Range Tests (26.51 and 8.63g/kg in 0-15cm and 15-30cm soil depths respectively), while that of other aggregate size fraction were not different from each other (Table 2). This implies that smaller aggregate fraction stores SOC more compare to lager fraction, confirming the findings of Adesodun *et al.*, (2005) and Oyedele *et al.*, (2014). Akinde (2018) reported that 63µm-250µm sized aggregate fraction contributed more to SOC protection than both 250µm-1mm and 1mm-2mm aggregate size fraction. They found out that SOC associated with the smaller aggregate fraction were more stabilized against mineralization. Similarly, significantly more TN were associated with 63µm-250µm sized soil aggregate fraction (3.35 and 2.79g/kg in 0-15cm and 15-30cm soil depths respectively), while 1-2mm aggregate fraction was the least (Table 2).

This could be due to the fact that smaller sized aggregate contained more SOC. It has been established that most of the nitrogen in soil are of organic origin (Silva and Mendonca, 2007). This result corroborates the findings of Adesodun *et al.*, (2005) who observed a greater TN in smaller sized soil aggregate fraction. The CEC associated with the soil aggregate fractions was not significantly

different from one another both at the surface and sub-surface soils, though <63µm sized soil aggregate fraction had the highest value at both depths (2.33 and 2.04cmol/kg 0-15cm and 15-30cm soil depths respectively) (Table 2). Higher value of CEC in <63µm sized soil aggregate fraction could be attributed to higher silt and clay fraction in this fraction (Igwe and Nkemakosi, 2007). Jiang *et al.* (2011) reported higher exchangeable cations in the in <63µm sized soil aggregate fraction indicating that this aggregate fraction has higher CEC.

Effects of land-use on CEC distribution within soil aggregates size fractions

The CEC distributions within the aggregate classes were significantly different across the land-use types (Figure 1). The CEC under CL and CCL ranked highest when compared to other land-use types while SFL was observed to be lowest among the land-use types and across all the aggregate size fractions. The unexpected trend the CEC followed in soil of SFL and CCL could prompt further research into the clay mineralogy and other factors that affects CEC. This was also recommended by Akinde *et al.*, (2020) who observed similar trend in the CEC of the land-use types. Forest soils have been reported to be characterized by high CEC and CCL with lower CEC (Wakene and Heluf, 2003).

The high CEC under cocoa land-use can be attributed to the relatively high clay and OC content of its soil and by extension its aggregates, being a sandy clay loamy soil at both depths. Oyebiyi *et*

Table 2: Distribution of cation exchange capacity, soil organic carbon and total nitrogen in the soil aggregate class fraction at 0-15 and 15-30cm soil depths

Soil depth	Soil Parameters	Soil Aggregate size fraction			
		<63µm	63µm-250µm	250µm-1mm	1mm-2mm
0-15cm	SOC (g/kg)	nd	26.51a	12.91b	6.91b
	TN (g/kg)	nd	3.35a	2.97b	2.67c
	CEC (cmol/kg)	2.33a	2.24a	2.16a	2.02a
15-30cm	SOC (g/kg)	nd	8.63a	6.29b	6.32b
	TN (g/kg)	nd	2.79a	2.40b	2.32b
	CEC (cmol/kg)	2.04a	1.84a	1.91a	1.88a

Means with the same letter in a row are not significantly different (P<0.05) according to Duncan's New Multiple Range Test.

nd= not determined, CEC= cation exchange capacity, SOC= soil organic carbon, TN= total nitrogen

al., (2018) reported that soil clay and OC are the major contributor to soil CEC. Tan (1998) reported that clay soils ordinarily carry an electronegative charge which gives rise to cation exchange reactions.

Effects of land-use on SOC distribution within soil aggregates size fractions

In soil OC (Figure 2), there were significant different across the land-use in each aggregate size classes except soil under oil palm which was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) at 1mm- 2mm aggregate size fraction. This might be resulting from the fibrous and dense root system of oil palm. This result corroborates the findings of Akinde (2018), who considered similar land-use types, and found out that oil palm plantation had most of its soil OC fractions concentrated in the 1mm-2mm sized soil aggregate fraction. Concentration of SOC is dependent on both the above ground and below ground biomass (plant root inclusive) (Zhang *et al.*, 2013). The fibrous rooting system of oil palm might have resulted in high amount of root fragments associated with 1mm-2mm sized soil aggregate fraction, hence, high soil OC contents within this soil aggregate fraction. Soil OC under TL was significantly greater than CCL in both $63\mu\text{m}$ - $250\mu\text{m}$ and in $250\mu\text{m}$ -1mm. Likewise, other land-use except that of OL were statistically greater than CCL at $250\mu\text{m}$ -1mm. However, at both 63 - $250\mu\text{m}$ and $250\mu\text{m}$ -1mm aggregates size, there was a decreasing trend from other land-use types to CCL as could be observed from the chart (Figure 2). This could be due to land preparation activities which induce soil disturbance and expose soil OC to rapid decomposition (Oyedede *et al.*, 1999).

Effects of land-use on TN distribution within soil aggregates size fractions

Total nitrogen contents of the SFL, PL and the tree crops land-use types were not significantly different from one another within all the soil aggregate size fractions except for $250\mu\text{m}$ -1mm sized aggregate

fraction where SFL had the significant highest (3.33g/kg) (Figure 3). CCL had the least TN content across the soil aggregate size fractions (2.04, 1.82 and 1.74g/kg in $63\mu\text{m}$ - $250\mu\text{m}$, $250\mu\text{m}$ -1mm and 1-2mm sized aggregate fraction respectively).

This result corroborates Tan *et al.*, (2007) who reported that forest soil contained considerably high amount of nitrogen. Forest is made up of numerous assemblage of plant species (including nitrogen fixing species) which may likely improve the soil nutrient (nitrogen inclusive). Deng *et al.*, (2016), and Deng and Shangguan (2016) reported that successional vegetation plays an essential role in improving soil nitrogen content.

Generally, the TN content in the soils of SFL, PL and the tree crops land use types could be attributed to their SOC content. Statistically, there was little to no variation in their soil OC content (Figure 2) and most of the nitrogen in soil has been reported to be of organic origin (Silva and Mendonca, 2007). In addition, animal wastes (faeces and urine) contains high amount of nitrogen (McNaughton *et al.*, 1997), which would have contributed to the TN content of paddock soil. The least TN content in the soil of continuously cropped land could be attributed to its low soil OC content (Figure 2). It could also be due to the fact the land is continuously cultivated with maize (*Zea mays*) (Akinde *et al.*, 2020). It has been established that maize requires high amount of nitrogen (Galindo *et al.*, 2019). It might also be due to volatilization of nitrogen resulting from increased oxidation of nitrogenous compounds in the soil. This may have been triggered by high exposure of the soil to air and increased temperature by frequent tillage operations. Also, the ability of nitrogen to be mobile in the soil might have possibly resulted into nitrogen losses by leaching. Oguike and Mbagwu (2009) reported similar result, they stated that continuous cultivation of soils caused a substantial loss of nitrogen due to increased volatilization and leaching.

Figure 1: Influence of land-use on CEC distributions within aggregate size fractions. SFL =Secondary Forest; TL = Teak Plantation; OL = Oil palm Plantation; PL = Paddock; CL = Cocoa Plantation; and CCL = Continuous cropping.

Figure 2: Influence of land-use on SOC distributions within aggregate size fractions . SFL =Secondary Forest; TL = Teak Plantation; OL = Oil palm Plantation; PL = Paddock; CL = Cocoa Plantation; and CCL = Continuous cropping.

Figure 3: Influence of land-use on TN distributions within aggregate size fractions SFL =Secondary Forest; TL = Teak Plantation; OL = Oil palm Plantation; PL = Paddock; CL = Cocoa Plantation; and CCL = Continuous cropping

Effects of various agricultural land-use types on CEC, SOC and TN of the whole soil

The CEC value under CL and CCL were statistically similar, but were significantly higher compared to other land-use types (Figure 4). Secondary forest unexpectedly had the least value of CEC. This unexpected observation could be due to other factors that affects CEC (Akinde *et al.*, 2020), such as clay mineralogy, leaching, low content of basic cations in the parent material and proportion of clay (Muche *et al.*, 2015). The highest value observed under cocoa plantation land-use could be due to its clay and organic carbon content. However, continuous fertilizer application into CCL may lead to increase in concentration of cation because depletion of organic carbon and intensive cultivation is expected to reduce the CEC of the soils (Kiflu and Beyene, 2013).

The soil OC of the land-use types were statistically the same except for the CCL which is also the least in value (Figure 5). The very low concentration of organic carbon (OC) observed under CCL was probably related to the increased oxidation of the soil organic carbon (SOC) due to increased disturbance of the soil by continuous and intensive tillage operations resulting in reduction in SOC and soil structure (Lal *et al.*, 1998). This is coupled with low vegetation cover that exposed the soil to intense heat of the sun. This observation is also similar to the report of Balesdent *et al.*, (2000) who stated that soil aeration was increased by tillage while the climate of the topsoil with respect to temperature and moisture was altered leading to an increased rate of SOC decomposition.

Figure 4: The CEC of soil under different land-use

Figure 5: The SOC of soil under different land-use

Total nitrogen (TN) content of soils under the different land-use types were different though TL, PL and OL were statistically the same. The highest ($P < 0.05$) was observed at the secondary forest land-use while the least value was observed under continuous cropping land-use (Figure 6). The relatively very low value of TN observed under CCL may be due to its low SOC content. It can also be due to volatilization of nitrogen resulting from increased oxidation of nitrogenous compounds in the soil (Oguike and Mbagwu, 2009). Oguike and Mbagwu (2009) reported similar result, they stated that continuous cultivation of soils caused a substantial loss of nitrogen due to increased volatilization and leaching. This may have been triggered by high exposure of the soil to air and increased temperature by frequent tillage operations.

Also, the increased mobility of nitrogen caused by incessant pulverization of the soil possibly resulted to losses by leaching. On the other hand, the relatively high value of total N observed under forest land-use may be due to the micro-climate created by adequate vegetation cover of the area which increased return of residues and reduced disturbance of soils which moderated the soil temperature, air and moisture against total N loss by volatilization. Percival *et al.*, (2000) reported that soils under pasture always resulted in better soil aggregation and carbon sequestration than in tilled crop lands. Generally, decrease in cultivation increases SOC and TN content Aweke *et al.*, (2013).

Conclusion

The results revealed that soil OC, TN and CEC were more associated with smaller sized soil aggregate fraction ($<63\mu\text{m}$, and $63\mu\text{m}-250\mu\text{m}$ sized soil aggregate fractions). This implies that smaller sized aggregate fraction contributes immensely to availability of nutrient in the soil and, hence, crop productivity. Therefore, land management practices should be geared towards preventing the loss of smaller sized aggregate, especially, to erosion. The study also showed that, all the land-use types considered had most of their soil OC and TN associated with smaller sized soil aggregate fraction ($63\mu\text{m}-250\mu\text{m}$), except for oil palm plantation, which had most of its soil OC associated with larger sized soil aggregate (1mm-2mm). In the whole soil, continuously cropped land had the least soil OC and TN which was due to land management activities associated with cultivation. The unusual trend followed by the CEC, especially, in secondary forest and continuously cultivated land could prompt further study into factors that affects CEC.

Conclusively, land-use type affects the distribution of SOC, TN and CEC associated with soil aggregate fractions. Most of the land-use type had their SOC, TN and CEC associated with micro-aggregates ($<250\mu\text{m}$ sized soil aggregate fraction) except for oilpalm plantation. Land-use practices that protects the land from losing its

Figure 6: The TN of soil under different Land-uses

micro-aggregates (such as conservative tillage, mulching, manuring, erosion control etc.) should be encouraged to conserve the soil nutrients. In addition, adoption of restorative land-uses such as tree-based cropping system and other less intensive cultivation practices are required to stabilize soil organic carbon, minimize nutrient loss and make for sustainable use of soil resources in the study area.

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